

OSOBNOSTI PROMENA NIVOVA PODZEMNIH VODA NA TERITORIJI „ AURUBIS BUGARSKA “A.D.

PECULIARITIES OF CHANGES IN GROUNDWATER LEVELS ON THE TERRITORY OF "AURUBIS BULGARIA" AD

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ABSTRACT: "Aurubis Bulgaria" AD is the largest metallurgical plant in Bulgaria. In order to preserve water resources, a monitoring network has been built to track the quantitative and qualitative indicators of groundwater in the territory affected by the production. The analysis of groundwater level monitoring data for the period 2010-2023 shows diversity in the trends of water level changes and their correlation with the geological and hydrogeological conditions of the area. The dynamics of groundwater level changes and their relationships with the content of certain pollutants in the groundwater have been examined.

Key words: groundwater, monitoring, copper production, Bulgaria

INTRODUCTION

The metallurgical industry is extremely important for the economy of any country. Production activities related to this industry often lead to negative impacts on various components of the environment, including groundwater (Gerginov, Krastanov, 2008; Sandru, Elena, 2017). An important tool for monitoring the condition of the groundwater in the territory affected by the production is the organization of a monitoring network and the processing of the obtained results (Albert et al., 2004; Everett, 1984). Besides the change of the content of potential pollutants in the water, an important element is the monitoring of groundwater level changes, as an indicator characterizing the quantitative state of the groundwater (Taylor, Alley, 2001). Changes in hydrodynamics represent one of the main factors influencing the migration of pollutants.

The subject of the present study is the groundwater in the area of the "Aurubis Bulgaria" copper mining plant, with the aim of determining the characteristics of groundwater levels changes based on monitoring measurements conducted during the period 2010-2023.

CHARACTERISTIC OF THE STUDIED OBJECT

The copper mining plant of "Aurubis Bulgaria" AD is located between the towns of Zlatitsa and Pirdop in the central part of Bulgaria (Fig. 1). It was built and started functioning in the period 1955–1959. The main activity is the primary metallurgical production of anode copper from copper concentrates and of cathode copper through electrolytic refining of anode copper, sulfuric acid and sludges are obtained as a by-product of both productions.

The main tectonic structure in the area is the Pirdop Graben (Fig. 1) (Cheshitev et al., 1995). It is one-sided, bounded to the north by the Sub-Balkan fault, territorially including the Pirdop and Zlatitsa fields. The graben is filled with Quaternary proluvial deposits with a thickness of up to 100 m, lying on a bedrock of metamorphic rocks - biotite and muscovite gneisses, but they may also lie on Pliocene deposits. The alluvial fans build the uppermost parts of the geological section. They are represented by gravels (coarse, medium, and fine), gravelly-sandy clays, and sandy clays. Clayey sands are relatively less common (Cheshitev et al., 1995). The different lithological types intertwine intricately and irregularly. The bedrock dips generally to the south. Its rocks also form the northern slope of the Sredna Gora Mountain, south of Pirdop and Zlatitsa, as well as small sections of the southern slope of the Balkan Mountain, west of Zlatitsa and east of Pirdop.

Figure 1. Geological scheme of the area around "Aurubis Bulgaria" plant (after Cheshitev et al., 1995)

In the area of the "Aurubis Bulgaria" plant, the groundwater formed in the gravels and sands of alluvial and proluvial origin are widespread. The water-bearing bodies are layers and lenses, often not interconnected, interbedded with impermeable sandy clays and gravelly clays. Their thickness is 10–40 m, thinning to the south. The formed underground flow has a direction of movement from north to south with local changes around the big rivers (Antonov, Danchev, 1980). The depth of the water level in the northern periphery of the Pirdop graben is 30–40 m, in the central part it is from 2 to 7 m, and in the southern part it is close to the surface, where swamps or areas with a shallow water level are formed.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In 1997, the plant was privatized and the first environmental assessment was made. In 1999, the construction of a monitoring network for observing the quantities and qualities of groundwater began (Hristov et al., 2017). The purpose of the monitoring is to track changes in the hydrodynamic and hydrochemical conditions of the groundwater in the affected area by the plant's activities.

Initially, 26 monitoring wells are constructed, whose number increases over the years and reaches 70 at present. They are located in an uneven network, both on the territory of the plant's production site and in adjacent areas (Mihaylova et al., 2019, 2023). In each monitoring well, water level, water temperature, pH, and conductivity are measured four times a year (seasonally), and a water sample is taken to determine the concentrations of As, Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Hg, Mn, Ni, Pb, SO₄, Zn. Each monitoring session has its own sequential number, and since the beginning of the monitoring program until now 98 sessions have

been conducted. Sampling and measurements are carried out according to the requirements of Bulgarian and European regulatory documents, while the chemical analysis of the collected water samples is performed by an accredited laboratory.

For the purposes of the present study, the series of data from measurements of groundwater levels in 59 monitoring points in the period 2010 - 2023 were used. The data for each well was processed separately according to accepted monitoring methodologies (Gibbons et al., 2009, Quevauviller et al., 2009). Graphs have been prepared and the trend for the change of the observed indicator over time for each point has been determined. Using GIS, hydrodynamic maps were prepared for each individual session. Visualization of some statistical indicators characterizing the changes in the water level in the studied area has also been obtained. A preliminary analysis was conducted to establish whether there is a correlation between the water level and the concentrations of certain pollutants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After processing the data, it is established that the nature of the water level changes in the monitoring wells is different, most likely due to the geological-hydrogeological structure of the studied area. The widespread proluvial deposits, formed by clays, sandy clays, clayey sands, and sands irregularly passing into each other vertically and horizontally, are characterized by filtration anisotropy. In areas where sandy materials with higher permeability prevail, water level fluctuations are within a narrow range, often below 0.5 m (Fig. 2a), while in areas dominated by clay deposits, the amplitudes are much larger - more than 2- 3 m (Fig. 2b). The trends in water level changes over time are also different. In 67 percent of the monitoring wells, it is found that there is a gradual decrease in the level of groundwater (Fig. 2c), in 26 percent of them - an increase in the level (Fig. 2d), and in only 7 percent of them there is no general trend for level change (Fig. 2a and b). The most likely reason for the different trends is the significant and irregular disruption of the groundwater flow structure by industrial buildings and facilities, with varying depths of construction excavations and foundations.

Figure 2. Change in water levels in selected monitoring points. a) monitoring well PE48; b) monitoring well PE35; c) monitoring wells PE15 and PE22; d) monitoring wells PE8 and PE64.

The spatial analysis of the data from the monitoring observations shows that during all sessions there are no significant changes in the flow structure. Movement is from north to south. According to the compiled map of water level amplitudes (Fig. 3), it is established that the area with the smallest fluctuations is in the central part of the plant site. This suggests that here we have a relatively thicker and more uniform water-conducting medium that mitigates the impact of rainwater passing through the aeration zone. In the

east and west, the amplitudes are higher, which suggests a more significant influence of rainwater infiltration. The standard deviation map has a similar character.

Figure 3. Location of the monitoring points of "Aurubis Bulgaria" and changes in the amplitude of the water levels

Also interesting is the problem of the relationship between the dynamics of groundwater and changes in the concentration of some pollutants. For some of the monitoring points, such a connection is not established, but for others, it is found that such an impact exists. For example, in well PE15, there is an increase in pH values almost every time the water level rises, indicating dilution of contaminated water likely due to rainfall infiltration (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Changes in water level and hydrochemical indicators. a) changes in water level and pH values in monitoring well PE15; b) changes in water level and concentration of SO_4 in monitoring well PE22

There is an increase in SO_4 concentrations when the water level rises in monitoring point PE 22 (Fig. 4). This is probably also due to rainfall infiltration, but they pass through the aeration zone, where zones of old contamination are presumed to exist.

These data show that the analysis of the relationship between water level fluctuations and changes in the content of observed hydrochemical parameters allows to locate areas with old pollution not revealed on the surface.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of the groundwater monitoring data in the area of "Aurubis Bulgaria" AD for the period 2010-2023 shows diversity in the trends of groundwater levels over time. Decreases in groundwater levels are more common than increases, with only a small percentage of wells showing no clear trend. The geological and hydrogeological conditions of the area play an important role in the dynamics of groundwater. Spatial data analysis is an important tool for understanding groundwater dynamics and allows the localization of areas with different characteristics. Different types of deposits lead to different amplitudes of water level fluctuations and different trends over time. The analysis shows that changes in the content of some pollutants, such as sulfates and pH, are related to fluctuations in water levels. This can help identify areas of old contamination that are not exposed on the surface. Further research and analysis are needed to better understand the relationship between groundwater dynamics and the various factors that determine it.

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